

Neural Computing based Part of Speech Tagger for Arabic Language: A review study

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Abstract— this paper aims to explore the implementation of part of speech tagger (POS) for Arabic Language using neural computing. The Arabic Language is one of the most important languages in the world. More than 422 million people use the Arabic Language as the primary media for writing and speaking. The part of speech is one crucial stage for most natural languages processing. Many factors affect the performance of POS including the type of language, the corpus size, the tag-set, the computation model. The artificial neural network (ANN) is modern paradigms that simulate the human behavior to learn, test and generalize the solutions. It maps the non-linear function into a simple linear model. Several researchers implemented the POS using ANN. This work proves that the using of ANN in utilizing the POS is achieving very well results. The performance has based the rate of accuracy, which most of the proposed models were obtained high accuracy between 90% and 99%. Besides, the using of neural models required less number of tag-sets for training and testing of the model. Most of NLP applications required accurate and fast POS, which is offered by the neural model.

Index Terms— Machine Learning, Natural Language Processing, Artificial Neural Network, POS, Arabic Text.

I. INTRODUCTION

The great development of information technology has helped to develop a set of algorithms that help the machine to learn and perform many functions of what man does. On the one hand, natural languages are one of the important means of transmitting information and exchanging experiences among humans [1]. Arabic is one of the five most important natural languages in the world where a large number of Arab and Islamic people are used because it is the language of the Quran they believe in. Hence the importance of studying the Arabic language and developing programs and applications. The vast amount of information in Arabic on the Internet requires that they focus on finding effective solutions to address the Arabic language [2].

Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) are a set of techniques that rely on simulating the work of biological neural networks. These systems learn to perform tasks by simulating the work of previous examples of any system and then generalize the model to simulate unseen data that has not been tested previously [3]. It is fast and accurate and can work with systems that are governed by a mathematical model and with little data.

ANN's work is based on a group of connected units called artificial neurons that stimulate neurons in the biological brain. The synapses in the brain are biological, where a signal is transferred from one artificial neuron to

another. The artificial nerve receives and processes a signal and then transmits the output to additional artificial nerve cells associated with it.

ANN has the ability to handle nonlinear processes and models and transform them into simple controllable linear models. Artificial neural networks have therefore been applied in many applications in a wide range of disciplines such as vehicle control, weather forecasting and process control, natural resource management, radar detection, face recognition, signal classification, sequence recognition, handwriting recognition, medical diagnosis, and more [4].

Part-of-speech tagging is the process of mapping a word in the text as matching to a particular part of speech. POS tagging is not just producing words and their parts of speech. It is a hard task because some words has more than one part of speech at different times or unspoken. Part-of-speech tagging is one of the most critical text analysis tasks used to classify words into their part-of-speech. There is a hierarchy of tasks in NLP, at the bottom is a sentence and word segmentation. POS tagging builds on top of that, and phrase chunking builds on top of POS tags. Therefore, POS tagging is considered one of the essential tasks for any NLP applications [5].

This paper explores the implementation of artificial neural networks (ANNs) in the part of speech tagger for the Arabic language. ANN has been used and applied successfully in many different applications such as text mining, text extraction and retrieval, pattern recognition, classification and generation of Arabic text, and speech recognition.

II. ARABIC LANGUAGE SPECIFICATIONS

Arabic is consider as one of the most elegant languages in the world today. It is one of the most spoken languages, ranking fifth behind English and Hindi. According to the latest published statistics, more than 240,000,000 people speak Arabic as their first language. The studies show that there are two versions of the Arabic language. Standard Arabic is the language used in the Qur'an used by religious scholars to teach academically. Modern Standard Arabic (MSA) is used and understood in the daily dealings used by Arabic speakers around the world. It is the primary language used by writers, politicians and the media and used in schools that teach Arabic as a foreign language.

The Arabic alphabet consists of 28 characters as shown in Figure 1. However, only three of these are vowels. These three symbols have five different variations, which means that the majority of the Arabic words contain static

characters. Unlike most other natural languages, Arabic is written in the script. This Arabic alphabet is one of the most important written languages of the world because of its distinctive form. It is written from right direction to left, unlike Latin languages, which are written from left to right. However, numbers are written from left direction to right [6].

خ	ح	ج	ث	ت	ب	ا
kha	haa	jiim	thaa	taa	baa	alif
ص	ش	س	ز	ر	ذ	د
saad	shiin	siin	zaay	raa	thaal	daal
ق	ف	غ	ع	ظ	ط	ض
qaaf	faa	ghayn	ayn	thaa	taa	daad
ي	و	ه	ن	م	ل	ك
yaa	waaw	ha	nuun	miim	laam	kaaf

Figure 1: Arabic letters with Romanization

Morphology is defined as part of linguistics that deals with the internal structure and word formation processes. A morpheme is often the smallest expressive and meaningful unit of language so that it cannot be divided into smaller parts. There are two types of morphemes: roots and the affixes. The root is defined as the basic form of the word formation which has the main meaning, while affixes are added at the beginning, middle or end of the root to produce new words that give additional meaning to different types as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Arabic Language Morpheme Classification

The Arabic has two types of gender: masculine and feminine. Also, Arabic words can be singular, bilingual or plural. Besides, each word can be a noun, verb or adjective. Vowels in Arabic are a distinctive feature that does not exist in Western languages. There are three short vowels in Arabic text, called fatHa, Damma and kasra which makes it more complicated for writing and understanding than other languages. The diacritical signs are also nominal, initial, or significant as shown in Figure 3.

Arabic letter with Short Vowel	حَ	حِ	حُ
Short Vowel Name	Kasrah	Fathah	Dammah
Short Vowel placement	Bottom	Top	Top
Short Vowel Sound	i	a	u
Similar English Sound	The "i" in sit	The "a" in ba	The "u" in put

Figure 3: the short vowels in Arabic text

III.RELATED WORKS

There are many researchers implemented that part of speech using different methods like Rule-based [7], Stochastic[8], Support Vector Machine (SVM)[9], Hidden Markov (HHM)[10] , Artificial Neural network (ANN)[11,12], and Hybrid models[13] as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Part of speech tagging models

Only a few works for implementing POS tagger for the Arabic Language based neural approaches as presented in Table 1. In reference [14] Yousif, J. H in 2006, utilize a recurrent neural network (RNN) for Arabic text, which obtained an Accuracy of 94.74% and MSE of 0.035697. Also, Jabar, H. Y. in 2006, reference [16] implements a multilayered perceptron (MLP) for tagging an Arabic text, which achieved an accuracy of 99.99% and MSE of 0.000109. In reference [13] Mohammed, N. F. also utilizes a multilayered perceptron (MLP) for tagging an Arabic text, which achieved an accuracy of 92%. Likewise, Muaidi, H. in 2014, reference [15], applied a back-propagation neural network (BPNN) for tagging Arabic tag sets. They achieved an accuracy of 98.83%. Lastly, Plank, B. 2016, in reference [17], employed Bidirectional long short-term memory (biLSTM) for tagging Arabic tag sets, which got an accuracy of 97.22%.

Other researchers’ implemented neural methods for tagging English text [20, 21, 22, 24, 26] as illustrated in Tbalet. They implemented different neural methods including multilayered perceptron (MLP), Stuttgart Neural Network Simulator (SNNS), Sparse Network of Linear

separators (SNOW), and Discrete-time recurrent neural networks (DTRNN), which obtained an accuracy between 85% and 97%. Also, some for other languages like Indian

[11, 19, 23] based MLP. Besides, Portuguese Languages [25] and Dutch Language [18].

Table 1: Related works of Part of Speech Tagger for tagging Arabic text

Author	Year	Location	Language	Accuracy/MSE	ANN Model
Yousif, J. H. [14]	2006	Malaysia	Arabic	Accuracy 94.74% MSE: 0.0356974	RNN
Jabar, H. Y [16]	2006	Malaysia	Arabic	Accurate 99.99% MSE: 0.000109	MLP
Mohammed, N. F., [13]	2012	Malaysia	Arabic	Accuracy 92%	MLP
Muaidi, H. [15]	2014	Jordan	Arabic	Accuracy 98.83%	BPNN
Plank, B., [17]	2016	Netherlands	Arabic	Accuracy 97.22%	biLSTM

Table 2: Related works of Part of Speech Tagger based different Languages

Author	Year	Location	Language	Accuracy/MSE	ANN Model
Schmid, H. [20]	1994	UK	English	Accuracy 96.22%	MLP
Marques, N.C [18]	1996	Portugal	Portuguese	Accuracy 97%	SNNS
Roth, D [24]	1998	UAS	English	Accuracy 97.13	SNOW
Perez-Ortiz, J. A. [22]	2001	Spain	English	Accuracy 92%	DTRNN
Ahmed [26]	2002	India	English	Accuracy 90.4%	MLP
Raju, S. B [21]	2002	India	English	Accuracy 85%	MLP
Poel, M. [25]	2008	Netherlands	Dutch	97.88 %	MLP
Parikh, A. [23]	2009	India	Indian	Accuracy 95.78 %	Multi-Neuro
Jabar H. Yousif [11]	2011	OMAN	Indian	Accuracy 82.8% MSE: 0.00564	MLP
Narayan, R [19]	2014	India	Indian	Accuracy 91.3%	MLP

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This paper discusses and reviews the implementation of neural methods in POS tagger for different Languages like Arabic, English, Indian and others. Only a few works for implementing POS tagger for the Arabic Language based neural approaches. Only a few works for performing POS tagger for the Arabic Language based neural approaches. Supervised neural models utilized for Arabic text as MLP such in references [13, 14, 16]. Besides, some of them use unsupervised models such as [14, 17]. In overall they achieved an accuracy between 94% and 99%.

Figure 5 illustrates the accuracy of some researchers that implementing POS tagging for Arabic text.

On the other side, several researchers performed neural methods for tagging other languages like English text [20, 21, 22, 24, 26], Indian [11, 19, 23]. Besides, Portuguese Languages [25] and Dutch Language [18]. They employed various neural schemes like MLP, SNNS, SNOW, and DTRNN. They obtained excellent results with an accuracy between 85% and 97%. Figure 6 depicted the results of POS tagger for these languages like English, Indian, Dutch, and Portuguese.

V. CONCLUSION

The main purpose of this paper is to explore and review the work done in the direction of implementation of ANN for implementing POS for Arabic text. The artificial neural network has been suggested as a modern method for introducing new solutions to solve the problems of the complexities of the Arabic language. The comparative study showed that most researchers used two significant methods for implementing the automatic POS. The first methodology is rule-based and the second methodology is relying on the science of statistics and calculations in the implementation of most POS-tagging models. Other researchers use a combination of methods (hybrid) to

utilize the POS and getting the desired results. The implementation of POS Tagging using ANNs and Genetic algorithms is a new strategy in utilizing and processing the Arabic text, but it had been used and employed successfully in several Arabic text applications such as text recognition and extracting and determining the roots and stems, and part-of-speech prediction. The current work proved that there is very little work concerning the use of neural networks and their techniques for the classification of Arabic text and the extraction of POS-tagging. The primary factor for checking the performance of the results is accuracy, but most researchers relied on their texts and used some different parts of the speech and tag-sets, which makes the comparison a complicated process.

Figure 5: Accuracy of works related Arabic text

Figure 6: Accuracy of works related Other Languages

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